

OVERCOMING THE LIMITATIONS OF ASHTAKAVARGA

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Abstract:

Just like D1 chart, the Ashtakavarga charts represent planetary positions at a given time and place but in mathematical form for easy analysis and prediction. The Ashtakavarga charts can be used for general astrological predictions and transit analysis.

Key Words: Ashtakavarga, Divisional Charts, Divisional Ashtakavarga, Brihat Parasara Hora Sastra (BPHS), Gochara (Transit), Sarvashtakavarga (SAV)

Introduction:

Ashtakavarga:

In Brihat Parasara Hora Sastra (BPHS), sage Parasara explained Ashtakavarga in Chapters 66 to 72. Sage Parasara says that the Ashtakavarga is an easy method to find happiness, sorrow and longevity. Ashtakavarga prediction is based on planetary position and transit analysis. This is same as prediction based on D1 chart (Janma Kundali). The Ashtakavarga charts are prepared without consideration of planet's functional nature (whether functional Benefic or functional Malefic) and their position in different functional houses (Bhavas). Ashtakavarga chart is representation of D1 chart in mathematical way using Bindus and Rekhās. Based on planetary positions and Lagna, the individual Ashtakavarga charts (AV) and Sarvashtakavarga (SAV) chart are derived.

Limitation of Prediction based on D1 Chart (General):

D1 chart is snapshot of planetary position at a given time and place. The D1 chart will be same for all the time period till when there won't be any Sign (Rashi) changes by either Navagrahas (9 planets) or Lagna (Ascendant). Typically, Lagna changes Sign in 2hrs and fastest moving planet, Moon changes Sign once in 2days 6Hrs. In a period of one sign change by Moon, the Lagna, approximately travels twice through whole 12 signs in Rashi chart leading to repeating same Lagna and planetary position twice.

Graha (Planet)	Time Spent in Each Sign (Rashi)	Time to Complete One Full Rotation Covering All 12 Signs
Lagna (Ascendant)	2 Hrs	1 Day
Surya (Sun)	30 Days	1 Year
Chandra (Moon)	2 Days 6 Hrs	27 Days
Kuja (Mars)	45 Days	1.5 Years
Budha (Mercury)	18 to 20 Days	~7 Months
Guru (Jupiter)	1 Year	12 Years
Shukra (Venus)	20 To 23 Days	~8 Months
Shani (Saturn)	2.5 Years	30 Years
Rahu and Ketu	1.5 Years	18 Years

In a given day, if the Navagrahas doesn't change their respective Signs, then there will be only 12 different possible D1 charts corresponding to 12 different Lagna. In fact, till any planet changes the Sign the same D1 chart repeats twice with duration of 2hrs each.

Limitations of Ashtakavarga:

Just like D1 chart, the Ashtakavarga and Sarvashtakavarga charts doesn't change and portray same Bindus and Rekhas for a period of 2hrs and repeat themselves twice within 2days. Hence Ashtakavarga can't provide accurate prediction.

Example 1:

The Ashtakavarga charts for twins born in few minutes apart will show same Bindus and Rekhas leading to same prediction for both twins which is may not be correct.

Example 1: Showing same Ashtakavarga charts for two different time periods (1hr apart)

Janma Kundali 1:

Date of Birth: 16 Sept 2023

Time of Birth: 05:00 AM

Place of Birt: Chennai, TN

	Ra (Ju)		
(Sa)	16 th Sept 2023 5:00am Chennai, TN		Ve
			Su
			Me
	Ke	Ma	Mo

24	25	34	38
27	SAV		27
26	16 th Sept 2023 5:00am Chennai, TN		23
29	30	30	24

Janma Kundali 2:

Date of Birth: 16 Sept 2023

Time of Birth: 06:00 AM

Place of Birt: Chennai, TN

	Ra (Ju)		
(Sa)	16 th Sept 2023 6:00am Chennai, TN		Ve
			Su
			Me
	Ke	Ma	Mo

24	25	34	38
27	SAV		27
26	16 th Sept 2023 6:00am Chennai, TN		23
29	30	30	24

Divisional Ashtakavarga:

To overcome this limitation of Ashtakavarga it is recommended to use Divisional Ashtakavarga. The divisional Ashtakavarga enables arriving at predictions with more accuracy. The divisional Ashtakavarga is derived from divisional charts and portray in mathematical format (Rekhas and Bindus) for easy analysis.

Case Study 1:

B.V. Raman (Astrologer)

Date and Time of Birth: Aug8 1912 at 7:38pm

Place of Birth: Bangalore

In D1 SAV the Lagan and 10H are with 26 and 25 points (average profession)

But in D24 SAV the Lagna and 9H are with 33 and 38 points (indicate higher Education)

31	28	33	33
26	D1 SAV		28
26			23
30	25	27	27

Case Study 2:

Sanjay Dutt (Lost mother in early age)

Date and Time of Birth: Jul 29 1959 at 15:00

Place of Birth: Mumbai

In D1 SAV the Lagan and 4H are with 26 and 28 points (High)

But in D24 SAV the Lagna and 2H are with 22 each (lack of support from parents)

32	30	33	28
28	D1 SAV		26
26			29
34	26	25	32

Conclusion:

Ashtakavarga given mathematical representation of planetary position and used to provide astrological prediction and transit analysis. Ashtakavarga limits analysis at D1 chart level and doesn't extend to division chart level.

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